

Atypical case of sex ratio disruption in Tabanidae collections with Malaise traps in Ecuadorian forests

Biologia

Jaime Buestán ^{a,b} and Gabriel A. Brito Vera ^{c*}

^a Honorary Professor at the Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Guayaquil, Guayaquil, Ecuador

^b Instituto Nacional de Biodiversidad (INABIO), Rumipamba 341 y Av. de los Shyris, Quito, Ecuador.

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1363-2193>

^c Department of Ecology, Faculty of Biological Sciences, Pontifical Catholic University of Chile, 7820436 Santiago, Chile. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0214-9979>

* Corresponding author: gabrielbrito1991@gmail.com

Table S1. The species represented in this collection correspond to specimens collected from seven localities in Ecuador.

Species	Locality	Female	Male	Total	F(%)	M(%)
<i>Dasybasis schineri</i> (Krober, 1931)	Tiquibuzo	16	50	66	24.24	75.76
<i>Esenbeckia testaceiventris</i> (Macquart, 1848)	Tiquibuzo	39	26	65	60.00	40.00
<i>Dicladocera tribonophora</i> Fairchild, 1958	Tiquibuzo	24	38	62	38.71	61.29
<i>Eristalotabanus violaceus</i> Krober, 1931	Tiquibuzo	7	36	43	16.28	83.72
<i>Dicladocera clara</i> (Schider, 1868)	Tiquibuzo	7	9	16	43.75	56.25
<i>Dicladocera macula</i> (Macquart, 1845)	Tiquibuzo	12	4	16	75.00	25.00
<i>Tabanus</i> sp.	Tiquibuzo	4	9	13	30.77	69.23
<i>Catachlorops</i> sp.	Tiquibuzo	5	5	10	50.00	50.00
<i>Scione</i> sp.	Tiquibuzo	9	0	9	100.00	0.00
<i>Spilotabanus multiguttatus</i> (Krober, 1930)	Tiquibuzo	0	1	1	0.00	100.00
<i>Esenbeckia testaceiventris</i> (Macquart, 1848)	Tinajillas	32	0	32	100.00	0.00
<i>Dasybasis montiun</i> (Surcuf, 1919)	Tinajillas	6	0	6	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera clara</i> (Schider, 1868)	Tinajillas	21	0	21	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera bellicosa</i> (Brethes, 1910)	Tinajillas	11	0	11	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera distomacula</i> Wilkerson, 1979	Tinajillas	7	0	7	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera nigrocoerulea</i> (Rondani, 1850)	Tinajillas	22	0	22	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera</i> sp. # 5	Tinajillas	98	0	98	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera</i> cf. <i>beaveri</i>	Tinajillas	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera</i> sp. # 15	Tinajillas	19	0	19	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera</i> sp.	Tinajillas	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera macula</i> (Macquart, 1845)	Tinajillas	2	0	2	100.00	0.00
<i>Eristalotabanus violaceus</i> Krober, 1931	Tinajillas	5	0	5	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione albifasciata</i> (Macquart, 1846)	Tinajillas	40	0	40	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione equivexans</i> Wilkerson, 1979	Tinajillas	10	0	10	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione maculipennis</i> (Schiner, 1868)	Tinajillas	711	0	711	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione obscurefemorata</i> Krober, 1930	Tinajillas	118	0	118	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 1-2	Tinajillas	279	0	279	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 5a	Tinajillas	58	1	59	98.31	1.69
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 6	Tinajillas	7	0	7	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 7	Tinajillas	4	0	4	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 13	Tinajillas	180	0	180	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 17	Tinajillas	18	0	18	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 23	Tinajillas	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 13	Tinajillas	2	0	2	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp.	Tinajillas	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Stenotabanus obscurus</i> Krober, 1929	Tinajillas	63	0	63	100.00	0.00
<i>Catachlorops</i> sp. # 7	Tinajillas	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Catachlorops</i> sp. # 6	Tinajillas	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Spilotabanus multiguttatus</i> (Krober, 1930)	Tinajillas	82	0	82	100.00	0.00
<i>Spilotabanus triaurius</i> Wilkerson, 1979	Tinajillas	9	0	9	100.00	0.00
<i>Scaptia sublata</i> Philip, 1969	Tinajillas	2	0	2	100.00	0.00
<i>Scaptia aureopygia</i> Krober, 1931	Tinajillas	2	1	3	66.67	33.33
<i>Scaptia rubriventris</i> (Krober, 1930)	Tinajillas	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Poeciloderas quadripunctatus</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	Tinajillas	7	0	7	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus rubiginipennis</i> Macquart, 1846	Tinajillas	607	1	608	99.84	0.16
<i>Dicladocera hirsuta</i> Wilkerson, 1979	Maylas	10	0	10	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera macula</i> (Macquart, 1845)	Maylas	52	0	52	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera nigrocoerulea</i> (Rondani, 1850)	Maylas	3	0	3	100.00	0.00
<i>Dicladocera</i> sp. # 9	Maylas	76	0	76	100.00	0.00

<i>Di cladocera</i> sp. # 10	Maylas	27	0	27	100.00	0.00
<i>Dasybasis montium</i> (Surcuf, 1919)	Maylas	17	0	17	100.00	0.00
<i>Dasybasis schineri</i> (Krober, 1931)	Maylas	41	0	41	100.00	0.00
<i>Spilotabanus multiguttatus</i> (Krober, 1930)	Maylas	12	0	12	100.00	0.00
<i>Spilotabanus triaurius</i> Wilkerson, 1979	Maylas	22	0	22	100.00	0.00
<i>Eristalotabanus violaceus</i> Krober, 1931	Maylas	5	2	7	71.43	28.57
<i>Scione equatoriensis</i> Surcuf, 1919	Maylas	70	5	75	93.33	6.67
<i>Scione obscurefemorata</i> Krober, 1930	Maylas	14	0	14	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 6	Maylas	6	0	6	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> cf. <i>flavohirta</i>	Maylas	1406	227	1633	86.10	13.90
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 3	Maylas	289	21	310	93.23	6.77
<i>Scione</i> sp. "A"	Maylas	4	0	4	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 8	Maylas	4	0	4	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> cf. <i>obscurefemorata</i>	Maylas	23	0	23	100.00	0.00
<i>Fidena rinophora</i> (Bellardi), 1859	Soroche	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Esenbeckia balzapambana</i> Snderlein, 1925	Soroche	16	0	16	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp. # 14	Soroche	3	0	3	100.00	0.00
<i>Scione</i> sp.	Soroche	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Bolbodimyia nigra</i> Stone, 1934	Soroche	2	0	2	100.00	0.00
<i>Bolbodimyia celeroides</i> Stone, 1964	Soroche	2	0	2	100.00	0.00
<i>Dichelacera submarginata</i> Lutz, 1915	Soroche	4	0	4	100.00	0.00
<i>Dichelacera</i> sp.	Soroche	0	2	2	0.00	100.00
<i>Philipotabanus fascipennis</i> (Macquart, 1845)	Soroche	21	0	21	100.00	0.00
<i>Philipotabanus magnificus</i> (Krober, 1934)	Soroche	6	0	6	100.00	0.00
<i>Stenotabanus detersus</i> (Walker, 1850)	Soroche	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Stypommisa changena</i> Fairchild, 1986	Soroche	5	0	5	100.00	0.00
<i>Stypommisa pequeniensis</i> (Fairchild, 1942)	Soroche	7	0	7	100.00	0.00
<i>Poeciloderas quadripunctatus</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	Soroche	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus colombensis</i> Macquart, 1846	Soroche	3	0	3	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus occidentalis</i> Oldroyd, 1954	Soroche	5	0	5	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus thiemeanus</i> (Enderlein, 1925)	Soroche	274	0	274	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus</i> cf. <i>colombensis</i>	Soroche	35	0	35	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus</i> cf. <i>bigoti</i>	Soroche	101	1	102	99.02	0.98
<i>Scione</i> sp.	Galán arriba	463	0	463	100.00	0.00
<i>Esenbeckia tigrina</i> Wilkerson, 1979	Galán arriba	5	0	5	100.00	0.00
<i>Fidena rinophora</i> (Bellardi, 1859)	Galán arriba	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Pytiocera ecuadorensis</i> Buestan & Krolow, 2015	Galán arriba	16	0	16	100.00	0.00
<i>Fidena</i> sp.	Galán arriba	3	0	3	100.00	0.00
<i>Philipotabanus</i> sp.	Galán arriba	311	0	311	100.00	0.00
<i>Stenotabanus bruesi</i> (Hine, 1920)	Galán arriba	4	0	4	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus colombensis</i> Macquart, 1846	Galán arriba	5	0	5	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus occidentalis</i> Oldroyd, 1954	Galán arriba	2	0	2	100.00	0.00
<i>Bolbodimyia celeroides</i> Stone, 1964	Plan de Milagro	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Dichelacera villavoensis</i> Fairchild & Philip, 1960	Plan de Milagro	14	0	14	100.00	0.00
<i>Catachlorops</i> sp. 1	Plan de Milagro	4	0	4	100.00	0.00
<i>Catachlorops</i> sp. 2	Plan de Milagro	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Di cladocera clara</i> (Schider), 1868	Plan de Milagro	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Di cladocera</i> sp. 1	Plan de Milagro	9	0	9	100.00	0.00
<i>Di cladocera</i> sp. 2	Plan de Milagro	9	0	9	100.00	0.00
<i>Stenotabanus obscurus</i> Krober, 1929	Plan de Milagro	7	0	7	100.00	0.00
<i>Stenotabanus</i> sp.	Plan de Milagro	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Stypommisa flavescens</i> (Krober, 1930)	Plan de Milagro	14	0	14	100.00	0.00

<i>Stypommisa anoriensis</i> Fairchild & Wilkerson, 1986	Plan de Milagro	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Stypommisa hypographa</i> (Krober, 1930)	Plan de Milagro	3	0	3	100.00	0.00
<i>Stypommisa</i> sp.	Plan de Milagro	1	0	1	100.00	0.00
<i>Poeciloderas quadripunctatus</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	Plan de Milagro	5	0	5	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus secundus</i> Walker, 1848	Plan de Milagro	111	1	112	99.11	0.89
<i>Tabanus hirtitibia</i> Walker 1850	Plan de Milagro	10	0	10	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus</i> sp.	Plan de Milagro	4	0	4	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus</i> sp.1	Plan de Milagro	21	0	21	100.00	0.00
<i>Tabanus antarcticus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Prosperina	280	4	284	98.59	1.41
<i>Tabanus colombensis</i> Macquart, 1846	Prosperina	1880	17	1897	99.10	0.90
<i>Tabanus occidentalis</i> var. <i>dorsovittatus</i>	Prosperina	833	27	860	96.86	3.14
<i>Tabanus pungens</i> Wiedemann, 1828	Prosperina	932	9	941	99.04	0.96
<i>Tabanus</i> sp.	Prosperina	1035	0	1035	100.00	0.00
<i>Lepiselaga crassipes</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	Prosperina	12	0	12	100.00	0.00
<i>Stenotabanus</i> sp.	Prosperina	0	1	1	0.00	100.00
<i>Esenbeckia tigrina</i> Wilkerson, 1979	Prosperina	20	0	20	100.00	0.00
<i>Pityocera ecuadorensis</i> Buestan & Krolow, 2015	Prosperina	4	0	4	100.00	0.00

Both the abundance of male and female individuals and their respective percentage values were recorded. The classification of some species was conducted according to the taxonomic criteria outlined by Buestán et al. (2007), who established a specific morphospecies framework. This classification has also been applied to the labeling of morphotypes currently housed at the National Institute of Biodiversity (INABIO). Therefore, if a detailed review is required, it is possible to consult the specimens deposited at INABIO using the classification system proposed by Buestán.